

A combination forecasting model based on IOWA operators

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Abstract. With respect to the combination forecasting problems with forecast value and actual value which are actual numbers. The relative distance measure is used as the induced value of the IOWA operator. A new fuzzy combination forecasting model is presented to minimize the error sum of squares. Finally, an example is illustrated to show this model improved the combination forecasting accuracy efficiently.

Key words: The relative distance measure; combination forecasting; IOWA operator.

The introduction

Since Bates and Granger put forward the combination forecast, it has long been one of the hot problems at home and abroad. Combination forecast, that is, considering the characteristics of each single prediction methods and combining different prediction methods. Combination forecasting can rally the merits of each single forecasting methods and overcome its shortcomings. Therefore, it has been widely used in many fields such as economy, statistics, society and so on [2-5]. Social environment is becoming more and more complicated, it is often difficult to obtain satisfactory results in the real life by simple combination of traditional real number combination forecasting. Yager has put forward the ordered weighted averaging (OWA) operator, it can effectively gather data. Yager has put forward the induced ordered weighted (IOWA) operator and probes into how to solve IOWA weight coefficient of combination forecast model. Then combination forecasting based on IOWA operator has attracted more and more attention from scholars both at home and abroad because of its excellent prediction effect. This paper [6] presents a combination forecasting method which is based on the prediction accuracy and the error sum squares. Based on the paper [6], paper [7] is based on the combination forecasting effectiveness. In paper [8], the interval-valued fuzzy combination forecasting method is proposed, which is based on the maximum and minimum closeness degree. The correlation coefficient is used as the guidance value in paper [9] and paper [10], and the least square distance is used as the standard in paper [11].

In this paper, based on the synthetic analysis of existed research results, the concept of relative distance measure is proposed and as the induced value of IOWA operator. And the combination forecasting model with the least square error sum is constructed. The example in this paper shows that the model can improve the prediction accuracy

Preliminary data

Definition 1^[12]. Set $OWA_w : R^n \rightarrow R$ as n-variate function, $W = (w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n)^T$ is a weighted vector related to

OWA_W , and it meet the requirements $\sum_{i=1}^n w_i = 1, w_i \geq 0, i = 1, 2, \dots, n$, if

$$OWA_W(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n) = \sum_{i=1}^n w_i b_i$$

The function OWA_W is 'n' dimension ordered weighted averaging (OWA) operator, b_i is the first i largest number among $a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n$ according the descending order.

Definition 2^[12-14]. Set $(\langle v_1, a_1 \rangle, \langle v_2, a_2 \rangle, \dots, \langle v_n, a_n \rangle)$ are 2d number array, make

$$IOWA_W(\langle v_1, a_1 \rangle, \langle v_2, a_2 \rangle, \dots, \langle v_n, a_n \rangle) = \sum_{i=1}^n w_i a_{v-index(i)}$$

$W = (w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n)^T$ is the weighted vector of, correspond $\sum_{i=1}^n w_i = 1, w_i \geq 0, i = 1, 2, \dots, n$, $v-index(i)$ is the coordinate under of the number among $v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n$ according descending order, then the function $IOWA_W$ is 'n' induction dimension ordered weighted average operator produce from $v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n$, for short $IOWA$ operator, v_i is induction of a_i .

In order to strengthen understanding, the paper gives an example: Set $\langle 3, 4 \rangle, \langle 1, 2 \rangle, \langle 5, 1 \rangle, \langle 7, 0 \rangle$ are 2d number array, $w = (0.3, 0.4, 0.2, 0.1)^T$ is the weighted vector of $IOWA_W$, then

$$\begin{aligned} IOWA_W(\langle 3, 4 \rangle, \langle 1, 2 \rangle, \langle 5, 1 \rangle, \langle 7, 0 \rangle) \\ = 0 \times 0.3 + 1 \times 0.4 + 4 \times 0.2 + 2 \times 0.1 = 1.4 \end{aligned}$$

The $IOWA$ operator has the following properties according to definition 2:

Lemma 1 (Monotonicity): Set $\langle v_1, a_1 \rangle, \langle v_2, a_2 \rangle, \dots, \langle v_n, a_n \rangle$ and $\langle v_1, a_1' \rangle, \langle v_2, a_2' \rangle, \dots, \langle v_n, a_n' \rangle$ are any two data vectors, and $a_i' \geq a_i$, then

$$IOWA_W(\langle v_1, a_1 \rangle, \langle v_2, a_2 \rangle, \dots, \langle v_n, a_n \rangle) \geq IOWA_W(\langle v_1, a_1' \rangle, \langle v_2, a_2' \rangle, \dots, \langle v_n, a_n' \rangle)$$

Lemma 2 (Commutativity): Set $\langle v_1, a_1' \rangle, \langle v_2, a_2' \rangle, \dots, \langle v_n, a_n' \rangle$ is arbitrary permutation data vector of $\langle v_1, a_1 \rangle, \langle v_2, a_2 \rangle, \dots, \langle v_n, a_n \rangle$, then

$$IOWA_W(\langle v_1, a_1 \rangle, \langle v_2, a_2 \rangle, \dots, \langle v_n, a_n \rangle) = IOWA_W(\langle v_1, a_1' \rangle, \langle v_2, a_2' \rangle, \dots, \langle v_n, a_n' \rangle)$$

Lemma 3 (Idempotency): Set $\langle v_1, a_1 \rangle, \langle v_2, a_2 \rangle, \dots, \langle v_n, a_n \rangle$ is any one data vectors, if $a_i = a, \forall i$, then

$$IOWA_W(\langle v_1, a_1 \rangle, \langle v_2, a_2 \rangle, \dots, \langle v_n, a_n \rangle) = a$$

Lemma 4 (Intermediate value property): Set $\langle v_1, a_1 \rangle, \langle v_2, a_2 \rangle, \dots, \langle v_n, a_n \rangle$ is any one data vectors, then

$$\min_i \{a_i\} \leq IOWA_W(\langle v_1, a_1 \rangle, \langle v_2, a_2 \rangle, \dots, \langle v_n, a_n \rangle) \leq \max_i \{a_i\}$$

Lemma 5. Set $\langle v_1, a_1 \rangle, \langle v_2, a_2 \rangle, \dots, \langle v_n, a_n \rangle$ is any one data vectors, if $v_i = a_i, \forall i$, then the $IOWA$ operator is degenerated into an OWA operator.

Combined forecasting model based on relative distance and IOWA operator

Set the actual value of the predicted object is represented by a sequence of $\{x_t\}_{t=1}^n$, there are m kinds of fuzzy single prediction method to predict it, make x_{it} to express predicted value of the i prediction method in the t moment, and $i=1,2,\dots,m, t=1,2,\dots,n$, make $L=(l_1, l_2, \dots, l_m)$ is the weighted vector of IOWA, correspond $\sum_{i=1}^m l_i = 1$ and $l_i \geq 0, i=1,2,\dots,m$.

Definition 3. Set

$$a_{it} = 1 - d(x_t, \hat{x}_{it}) / \sum_{i=1}^m d(x_t, \hat{x}_{it}), i=1,2,\dots,m; t=1,2,\dots,n, \quad (1)$$

the a_{it} is relative distance accuracy of the i prediction method in the t moment.

As can be seen from the definition 5: the greater the difference between the predicted value and the actual value, the lower the relative distance accuracy.

According to the formula (1), $a_{it} \in [0,1], i=1,2,\dots,m, t=1,2,\dots,n$, the relative prediction accuracy a_{it} is used as the guidance value of $\hat{x}_{it}$, m fuzzy single prediction method and relative prediction accuracy based on difference metric function constitutes m 2d number array, namely, $\langle a_{1t}, \hat{x}_{1t} \rangle, \langle a_{2t}, \hat{x}_{2t} \rangle, \dots, \langle a_{mt}, \hat{x}_{mt} \rangle$, according to definition 2 the following concepts can be obtained:

Definition 4^[13-14]. Set

$$IOWA_L(\langle a_{1t}, \hat{x}_{1t} \rangle, \langle a_{2t}, \hat{x}_{2t} \rangle, \dots, \langle a_{mt}, \hat{x}_{mt} \rangle) = \sum_{i=1}^m l_i \hat{x}_{a-index(it)} \quad (2)$$

$a-index(it)$ is the coordinate under of the number among $a_{1t}, a_{2t}, \dots, a_{mt}$ according descending order, the formula (2) called prediction value of triangular fuzzy number combination of IOWA operator induced by relative prediction precision sequence at t moment

As can be seen from the definition 4: after the IOWA operator is induced, the combined forecasting weight coefficients are independent of each fuzzy prediction method, but determined by the relative forecast accuracy of each fuzzy single item forecast, that is, the smaller the difference between the predicted value and the actual value of the first i fuzzy single prediction method at t moment, the corresponding weight is larger.

Definition 5^[9] Set the actual sequence of the predicted object is $\{x_t\}_{t=1}^n$, prediction sequence is $\{\hat{x}_t\}_{t=1}^n$, make

$SSE = \sum_{t=1}^n (\hat{x}_t - x_t)^2$ as the sum of squared error of prediction sequence and actual prediction.

Make $\delta_{a-index(t)} = x_t - \hat{x}_{a-index(it)}$, according to definition 3 and definition 4, the sum of squared error of the predicted value and the actual value can be obtained at n points, namely,

$$SSE_1 = \sum_{t=1}^n \left[x_t - \sum_{i=1}^m l_i \hat{x}_{a-index(it)} \right]^2 = \sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{j=1}^m l_i l_j \left[\sum_{t=1}^n \delta_{a-index(it)} \delta_{a-index(jt)} \right]$$

Based on possible point and IWOA operator of fuzzy combination for forecasting model, it can be expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned} \min \quad & SSE_1 = \sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{j=1}^m l_i l_j \left[\sum_{t=1}^n \delta_{a-index(it)} \delta_{a-index(jt)} \right] \\ \text{s.t.} \quad & \begin{cases} \sum_{i=1}^m l_i = 1 \\ l_i \geq 0, i = 1, 2, \dots, m \end{cases} \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

Then steps based on possible point and IWOA operator of fuzzy combination for forecasting model is given below:

- 1) Input the actual sequence, use of each single prediction methods for forecasting sequence as $\{\hat{x}_{it}\}_{t=1}^n, i = 1, 2, \dots, m$;
- 2) Formula (1) and Formula (2) is used to calculate relative distance precision a_{it} of each single prediction methods at all time points, $i = 1, 2, \dots, m; t = 1, 2, \dots, n$;
- 3) Regard relative distance precision of each single prediction methods at all time points as the induced value to build a binary array $(\langle a_{1t}, \hat{x}_{1t} \rangle, \langle a_{2t}, \hat{x}_{2t} \rangle, \dots, \langle a_{mt}, \hat{x}_{mt} \rangle)$, formula (2) is used to calculate combination forecast based on possible point and IOWA operator;
- 4) Formula (3) is used to build combination forecast model and calculate the weight coefficient;
- 5) Use the formula $\hat{x}_i = \sum_{i=1}^m l_i \hat{x}_{a-index(it)}$ to calculate combination forecast.

The example analysis

In this paper, we use the data in the literature [11] to explain the computational process of the proposed method and verify the effectiveness of this method, the prediction effect index system is error variance (SSE), mean absolute error (AE), average percentage error (APE) and the mean square error percentage (SPE),

$$SSE = \sum_{t=1}^n (x_t - \hat{x}_t)^2$$

$$AE = \sum_{t=1}^n |x_t - \hat{x}_t|$$

$$APE = \sum_{t=1}^n |(x_t - \hat{x}_t) / x_t|$$

$$SPE = \sqrt{\sum_{t=1}^n [(x_t - \hat{x}_t) / x_t]^2}$$

The steps of this method are as follows:

Step number one: the actual value sequence and the data of each single prediction methods are shown in table 1.

Table 1. Prediction Results of Three Kinds of Fuzzy Single Prediction Models

Time t	Actual value	Single method 1	Single method 2	Single method 3
1	72.5	75.7532	72.3747	72.5
2	74.3	72.6894	76.211	74.3
3	78.5	78.6441	80.0473	77.4076
4	83.8	81.9153	83,8836	81.0646
5	87.6	89.2122	87.7199	86.2824
6	93.1	91.5578	91.5562	90.7392
7	95.5	95.7235	95.3925	95.9793
8	102.7	104.171	99.2288	99.4672
9	104.3	105.6347	103.0651	105.5219
10	109.2	105.2278	106.9014	108.9521
11	109.4	111.8216	110.7377	113.0623
12	113.3	112.4537	114.574	114.7418
13	115.9	115.6816	118.4103	117.6775

Step number two: calculate relative distance precision of each single prediction methods at all time points, the results are shown in table 2:

Table 2. Relative Prediction Accuracy of Three Kinds of Single Prediction

Time t	1	2	3	4	...	11	12	13
Method 1	0.0015	0.5847	0.9942	0.6783	...	0.7216	0.8379	0.9950
Method 2	0.9985	0.4153	0.3365	0.9994	...	0.9151	0.6326	0.3373
Method 3	1.0000	1.0000	0.6693	0.3223	...	0.3633	0.5295	0.6677

Step number three: according to the relative prediction accuracy of each single prediction method at all time points to calculate combination forecast:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & IOWA_t (\langle 0.0015, 75.7532 \rangle, \langle 0.9985, 72.2747 \rangle, \langle 1, 72.5 \rangle) \\
 & = I_1 72.5 + I_2 72.2747 + I_3 75.7532 \\
 & IOWA_t (\langle 0.5847, 72.6894 \rangle, \langle 0.4135, 72.211 \rangle, \langle 1, 74.3 \rangle) \\
 & = I_1 74.3 + I_2 72.6894 + I_3 72.211 \\
 & \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \\
 & IOWA_t (\langle 0.9950, 115.6816 \rangle, \langle 0.3373, 118.4103 \rangle, \langle 0.6677, 117.6775 \rangle) \\
 & = I_1 115.6816 + I_2 117.6775 + I_3 118.4103
 \end{aligned}$$

Step number four: formula (3) is used to build combination forecast model and calculate the weight coefficient,

$$l_1 = 0.8768, \quad l_2 = 0.1232, \quad l_3 = 0$$

Step number five: use the formula $\hat{x}_i = \sum_{i=1}^m l_i \hat{x}_{a-index(it)}$ to calculate combination forecast.

In order to verify the effectiveness of the combined forecasting method proposed in this paper, table 3 shows the predicted values of the proposed method, table 4 gives the method proposed in this paper and the prediction results of each single prediction method.

Table 3. Predictive Value of This Paper

Actual value	Single method1	Single method 2	Single method 3	Single method in this paper
72.5	75.7532	72.3747	72.5	72.4846
74.3	72.6894	76.211	74.3	74.1016
78.5	78.6441	80.0473	77.4076	78.4918
83.8	81.9153	83.8836	81.0646	83.0858
87.6	89.2122	87.7199	86.2824	87.5428
93.1	91.5578	91.5562	90.7392	91.5576
95.5	95.7235	95.3925	95.9793	95.4333
102.7	104.171	99.2288	99.4672	103.5915
104.3	105.6347	103.0651	105.5219	105.2192
109.2	105.2278	106.9014	108.9521	108.6995
109.4	111.8216	110.7377	113.0623	110.8712
113.3	112.4537	114.574	114.7418	112.7149
115.9	115.6816	118.4103	117.6775	115.9275

Table 4. The Predicted Value of Each Method

	SSE	AE	APE	MSPE
Method 1	48.1294	20.5347	0.2232	0.59
Method 2	37.0499	17.5651	0.1791	0.38
Method 3	46.8712	19.5697	0.1990	0.48
Method in this paper	7.3344	6.9977	0.0704	0.01

As can be seen from table 3, in this paper, the combination method based on relative distance precision and IOWA operator is much better than the single prediction method, so the method in this paper is effective

and the method proposed in this paper is easier to compute. The weight coefficient $l_3 = 0$ does not mean that the third methods are invalid, because the IOWA operator is the combination of the predicted value of the sort of determined value and independent of the position of the single prediction value.

Conclusion

In this paper, the concept of relative distance precision is proposed and as the induced value of IOWA operator, establishing a combined forecasting model which takes the sum of error square sum as the minimum. The effectiveness of the model is verified by a numerical example in the paper. By predicting coherence, we can predict relative prediction accuracy of each individual fuzzy prediction in the next $n+T$ years, which is consistent with the average relative prediction accuracy of the past T years. Meanwhile, the idea of this paper can be extended to other combinatorial forecasting models.

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